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COMPARISON OF LUMBAR SACRAL PLEXUS BLOCK WITH SPINAL ANESTHESIA IN HIGH-RISK PATIENTS SCHEDULED FOR HIP SURGERIES

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ABSTRACT:

BACKGROUND:

High risk elderly patients with hip fractures were the greatest challenge to anesthesiologist as they are more prone to perioperative morbidity and mortality. Combined lumbar sacral plexus block have been an effective method of anaesthesia, also considerable in postoperative analgesia in high-risk patients of hip surgeries as it provides fewer complications, better homeostasis, hemodynamic control.

OBJECTIVES:

The aim of this study was to compare the efficacy of lumbar sacral plexus block with subarachnoid block in terms of onset and duration of sensory and motor blockade, hemodynamic changes and postoperative analgesia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This prospective randomized study was carried out in 50 patients aged 35-80 years and weighed 40 to 85 kg belonging to ASA physical status III/IV posted for hip surgeries. patients were divided into two groups, SAB (subarachnoid block) group and LSPB (lumbar sacral plexus block) group of 25 each by convenient sampling. Onset of sensory and motor blockade, hemodynamic changes, time for first rescue analgesic were noted and compared. Statistical analysis was done using SPSS Software.

RESULTS:

The perioperative heart rate and arterial blood pressure were more stable in LSPB group. Postop analgesia duration was significantly prolonged in LSPB group (11.4±1.7 hours) as compared to SAB group (4.3±0.43 hours). Hypotension and bradycardia noted in SAB group.

CONCLUSION:

Lumbo-sacral plexus block offered more stable intraoperative hemodynamic parameters and prolonged postop analgesia as compared to Subarachnoid block in high-risk patients undergoing hip surgeries.

KEYWORDS:

Lumbosacral plexus block, Spinal anaesthesia, Hip surgeries, Analgesia.

INTRODUCTION:

Modern anaesthesiologists are concerned with both intraoperative and postoperative pain relief⁽¹⁾. The most commonly used method of anaesthesia for hip surgeries is regional anaesthesia. subarachnoid block (SAB) and Peripheral nerve blockade are two techniques commonly used for lower limb surgeries. As compared to general anaesthesia, regional anaesthesia reduces the

number of complications as airway instrumentation and manipulation, venous thromboembolism, respiratory complication⁽⁹⁾. Regional anaesthesia has advantages of an early resumption of oral intake postoperatively which is needed in the management of diabetic patients and also reduces the chances of thromboembolic events. Although neuraxial anaesthesia has several disadvantages such as perioperative hemodynamic instability, urinary retention, epidural hematoma. Occasionally these may also lead to outcomes like myocardial infarction, stroke, CNS infection⁽⁹⁾. Newer techniques such as Peripheral nerve blocks provides hemodynamic stability and postoperative pain relief which improved patient satisfaction, early ambulation, decreased length of hospital stay and hospital cost. This study was done to compare the efficacy of LSPB and SAB in high-risk patients undergoing hip surgeries. The parameters measured for assessing the efficacy of two methods were the time for performing block, the time to achieving sensory and motor blockade, the time to the first request for analgesia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This study was carried out in total 50 patients of either sex, aged ≥ 35 years, ASA Physical status III/IV scheduled for hip surgeries. Patients were randomly classified into two groups, Group LSPB and group SAB. Each group included 25 pts. Group SAB received Spinal anaesthesia by heavy bupivacaine HCL 0.5 % 2.5 ml and group LSPB received Lumbosacral nerve block by 30 ml bupivacaine 0.375 % and lignocaine + adrenaline 1.5 %⁽⁷⁾. All patients were explained the risks and benefits of the procedure to be done and written informed consent was taken. All patients were assessed one day before the procedure by an anesthesiologist.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Patients with controlled respiratory and cardiac disease
- Elective surgeries
- Age 35-80 years
- Body weight 40-85 kg
- ASA Physical status II/III/IV

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Patients with allergy to local anesthetics
- Infection at local site
- Patients' refusal
- Patients having coagulopathy

RELATIVE CONTRAINDICATION⁽¹⁰⁾:

- presence of intrathecal pump or spinal cord stimulator
- Major lumbar spine deformity
- Prior major spinal surgery
- Pre-existing neurological deficit

A standard preoperative assessment was performed by an anaesthesiologist. It included medical history, physical examination, airway assessment, systemic examination. Basic routine investigations were done included complete blood count, blood grouping with Rh typing, random blood sugar, serum urea and creatinine, serum electrolytes, electrocardiography (ECG), chest x ray and echocardiogram if indicated. Special records about allergic history, a history of neuropathy or demyelinating disease, coagulopathy, and a history of chronic pain were taken. Current patient prescriptions including analgesics and anticoagulants should also be noted. The patients were kept NBM for at least 6 hours prior to the surgery. Routine monitoring such as ECG, Pulse oximetry (spo2), and non-invasive blood pressure. An intravenous cannula was inserted and intravenous fluid started after taking the patient inside the operative room. All patients were given intravenous midazolam 0.025 mg/kg as premedication. Supplemental oxygen was administered through a face mask at the rate of 4-6 L/min (3).

In group SAB was performed in sitting positing. Under all aseptic precaution painting and draping was done in lumbar region. 23 G Spinal needle inserted into L3-L4 Subarachnoid space. Inj. Bupivacaine HCL 0.5% heavy 2.5 ml was deposited after free and clear flow of csf.

In group LSPB were performed in lateral decubitus position with the operative limb in the uppermost position, with the hip and knees flexed. Preparation and draping of the operative lumbar region were done. The skin was infiltrated with a local anesthetic at the needle entry point.

Capdevielle's approach for lumbar plexus

After mid-line was palpated, identified the spinous process. A line was first drawn through the lumbar spinous process and both iliac crests were identified and connected with a line to approximate L4 level. The posterior superior iliac spine was palpated and a line was drawn cranially from the PSIS. A long stimulating needle was inserted at the point of intersection between the transverse (intercristal) line and the intersection of the lateral and middle thirds of the sagittal lines. The needle was introduced till the transverse process was hit either caudally or cranially by the "walked off" technique until the quadriceps femoris muscle twitches were obtained. The needle should never be inserted more than 3 cm deep into the transverse process. The current in the nerve stimulator was gradually decreased to 0.5 mA. Then inj. Bupivacaine 0.375 % 20 ml +inj. lignocaine+ adrenaline 1.5 % 10 ml was given after negative aspiration.

Approach for sacral plexus block

It was performed with the same position of the patient. The stimulating needle was introduced perpendicular to the gluteal muscle at the junction of the upper one-third and lower two-thirds of the line joining the PSIS and the ISCHIAL TUBEROSITY. Then if it hits the sacral plate, the needle tip was not advanced more than 1.5-2 cm. The response was noticed in form of plantar/dorsiflexion of the foot. Then inj. Bupivacaine 0.375 % 10 ml +inj. lignocaine+ adrenaline 1.5 % 10 ml was given after negative aspiration.

The time from the injection of drug to the loss of pinprick sensation over the incision site was defined as onset of sensory blockade.

The time from the injection of drug to the inability to extend the knee in the lumbar plexus block and the inability to dorsi/plantar flex the ankle joint in the sacral plexus block was defined as the onset of motor blockade.

The sensory blockade was evaluated over the limb at the incision site by 3-point scale.

Grade 0 - normal sensation

Grade 1 - loss of sensation of pinprick (analgesia)

Grade 2 - loss of sensation of touch (anaesthesia)

The motor blockade was evaluated by the inability of the patient to extend knee joint for lumbar plexus block and inability to dorsiflex/plantarflex the ankle joints in the sacral plexus block.

The motor blockade was assessed by modified Bromage scale⁽⁸⁾.

SCORE	CRITERIA
1	Complete block (Unable to move feet or knees)
2	Almost complete block (able to move feet only)
3	Partial block (just able to move knees)
4	Detectable weakness of hip flexion while supine (full flexion of knees)
5	No detectable weakness of hip flexion while supine
6	Able to perform partial knee bend

The onset of sensory and motor blockade and the duration of surgery was also noted. Intraoperative vitals were noted at every 15 minutes' intervals till the end of surgery. Patients were observed for 24 hours at interval of 1 hour for postoperative pain using (VAS) Visual analogue scale, vitals and for postoperative complications such as hematoma, ureteric injury, hypotension, arrhythmia etc. Patient was given inj. diclofenac sodium 75 mg IM as a rescue analgesic or (VAS) Visual analogue score was >4 and time recorded.

All the data were measured in mean and standard deviation. Statistical analysis was done using SPSS Software and analysed by unpaired student's 't' test and p value <0.05 was considered significant.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS:

TABLE 1: Demographic data

Parameters	SAB group(n=25)	LSPB group(n=25)	P
AGE (Years) Mean \pm SD	57 \pm 16.8	56.6 \pm 15.2	0.84(NS)
Sex (male/female)	12/13	11/14	
Weight (kilograms)	55 \pm 14.2	57 \pm 16.1	
ASA Physical status (III/IV)	11/14	12/13	
Duration of surgery(mins)	116.8 \pm 9.48	117.3 \pm 7.35	0.86(NS)

Demographic data including duration of surgery were compared in both groups.

TABLE 2: Onset of sensory and motor blockade

PARAMETERS	GROUP SAB	GROUP LSPB	P VALUE
Time for sensory blockade (mins)	2.63 \pm 0.6	18.3 \pm 2.5	<0.05 (S)
Time for motor blockade(mins)	7.6 \pm 0.8	24.76 \pm 2.6	<0.05 (S)

(S=Significant) (NS=non-significant)

Time required for sensory blockade was higher 18.3 \pm 2.5 mins in group LSPB as compared to 2.63 \pm 0.6 mins in group SAB which was statistically significant. Time required for motor blockade was more 24.76 \pm 2.6 mins in group LSPB as compared to 7.6 \pm 0.8 mins in group SAB which was statistically significant.

FIGURE:1 INTRAOPERATIVE MEAN PULSE RATE

FIGURE:2 POSTOPERATIVE MEAN PULSE RATE

In SAB group, pulse rate was significantly decrease 15 mins after spinal anaesthesia while in LSPB group, there was no change in pulse rate. Hypotension observed in 12 patients in group

SAB as compared to 2 patients in LSPB group. So, hemodynamically patients were stable in group LSPB as compared to group SAB.

TABLE 3: SYSTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE (mm of Hg)

TIME	SAB group	LSPB group	P value
Baseline	128.24±5.5	121.13±4.3	0.001
0 min	127.21±5.4	117.96±6.5	0.001
5 min	120.22±5.3	118.20±5.0	0.05
10 min	118.22±4.5	121.13±6.9	0.05
15 min	110.32±4.4	120.66±4.2	0.001
30 min	108.44±5.6	120.66±4.2	0.001
45 min	114.53±4.6	120.67±4.3	0.001
60 min	116.34±4.4	120.53±4.6	0.001
75 min	118.44±5.3	120.00±5.6	0.001
90 min	121.44±5.7	121.13±4.5	0.05
120 min	124.65±5.4	120.86±4.5	0.05
POST OPERATIVE			
3 hours	124.43±4.5	119.93±5.7	0.05
4 hours	123.34±4.5	120.86±4.1	0.05
5 hours	123.34±4.3	120.13±3.7	0.05
6 hours	122.43±5.4	115.53±6.9	0.05
7 hours	122.56±6.5	115.53±6.9	0.05
8 hours	121.34±5.6	121.13±4.3	0.05
9 hours	122.34±5.5	120.66±4.2	0.05
10 hours	124.45±4.4	120.66±4.3	0.05
11 hours	122.33±4.5	120.66±4.2	0.05
12 hours	121.56±6.4	121.40±4.6	0.05
15 hours	122.45±5.5	121.40±4.4	0.05
18 hours	123.56±5.5	120.66±4.3	0.05
21 hours	122.35±6.1	120.60±4.6	0.05
24 hours	121.53±4.7	118.20±4.9	0.05

TABLE 4: DIASTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE (mm of Hg)

TIME	SAB group	LSPB group	P VALUE
Baseline	79.86±3.6	80.56±4.2	0.05
0 min	76.80±5.1	78.47±4.5	0.05
5 min	72.67±5.3	77.35±4.5	0.05
10 min	70.46±6.4	78.54±4.6	0.05
15 min	66.54±6.2	77.57±5.7	0.05
30 min	64.45±5.4	75.65±5.7	0.05

45 min	66.45±4.5	78.58±6.7	0.05
60 min	70.34±3.4	77.67±7.8	0.05
75 min	72.45±5.5	79.56±5.6	0.05
90 min	72.35±5.4	78.77±4.5	0.001
120 min	73.45±5.4	77.57±5.7	0.001
POST OPERATIVE			
3 hours	73.45±5.6	78.58±7.8	0.001
4 hours	74.45±6.5	77.58±4.4	0.001
5 hours	74.56±5.6	76.67±6.7	0.001
6 hours	75.56±6.6	77.78±5.8	0.001
7 hours	76.67±6.7	77.78±5.6	0.001
8 hours	77.54±6.8	75.67±6.5	0.05
9 hours	76.74±4.5	77.67±5.6	0.05
10 hours	77.35±5.4	76.56±6.7	0.05
11 hours	78.45±4.4	75.67±4.5	0.05
12 hours	77.44±4.4	75.67±6.5	0.05
15 hours	77.59±6.5	77.67±5.6	0.05
18 hours	78.57±4.5	78.56±4.5	0.05
21 hours	77.57±5.6	77.56±5.6	0.05
24 hours	78.69±4.8	78.66±4.5	0.05

TABLE 5: Postoperative visual analogue scale (VAS) Score in both the group

Time interval in min	VAS score in Group SAB (Mean ± SD)	VAS score in Group LSPB (Mean ± SD)	'p' value
30	3.13 ± 1.1	1.4 ± 0.5	0.0001(S)
60	2.02 ± 1.1	1.7 ± 0.5	0.35(NS)
90	1.71 ± 1.02	2.2 ± 0.6	0.07(NS)
120	1.75 ± 0.4	1.74 ± 0.5	0.77 (NS)

VAS score at interval of 30 min was 3.13±1.1 in group SAB as compared to group LSPB (1.4±0.5) which was statistically significant. VAS score at interval of 60,90 and 120 mins were not statistically significant between group SAB and LSPB. Inj. diclofenac sodium 75 mg IM

was given in all patients whose VAS score was >4. Rescue analgesics were needed more in group SAB patients as compared to group LSPB patients.

TABLE 6: COMPARISON OF FIRST RESCUE ANALGESIC REQUIREMENT IN MINS IN BOTH THE GROUPS

	MEAN	SD	SEM	P VALUE
Group SAB	263.6	25.8	4.7	0.002
Group LSPB	689.0	107.4	20.7	

TABLE 7: COMPLICATIONS

Parameters	SAB group	LSPB group	P
Hypotension	12	2	
Bradycardia	10	2	
Nausea	3	0	0.235
Vomiting	0	0	
Pruritus	0	0	
Drowsiness	0	0	
Respiratory depression	0	0	

Fisher exact test

DISCUSSION:

In High-risk patient's general anaesthesia would result into higher complications due to the significant physiological changes and would also delay the postoperative recovery of these patients. Therefore, regional anaesthesia is preferred for lower limb surgeries in high-risk patients. Modern anaesthetists use combined lumbar sacral plexus block as it improves analgesia and reduce the analgesic requirement after hip surgeries⁽¹⁾. Several studies reported that LSPB was effective in providing prolonged postoperative analgesia. Rokhtabnak et al.⁽⁶⁾, study found that, a peripheral nerve block maintains a stable intraoperative parameter in severely cardiovascular compromised patients undergoing hip surgeries.

In this study both the groups (SAB) and (LSPB) were compared in terms of onset of sensory and motor blockade, hemodynamic changes and time for first rescue analgesic.

In LSPB group time required for onset of sensory and motor blockade was significantly higher as compared to SAB group⁽²⁾. We observed more hypotension (n=12) in SA group as compared to LSPB group(n=2). In this study there was no clinically significant fall in blood pressure in LSPB group, whereas 48 % of patients undergoing SAB developed a fall in blood pressure. So, LSPB is a good and effective alternative to SAB or general anaesthesia for hip surgeries. In a study of Amiri et al., LSPB provided excellent hemodynamic stability without intense variation in heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, mean arterial blood pressure^(4,5).

VAS score at 30 min was 1.4±0.5 in LSPB group as compared to 3.13±1.1 in SAB group, which was statistically significant. The result of the present study showed that LSPB was effective in providing prolonged postoperative analgesia and also decreases the rescue analgesic doses.

Complications like nausea, hypotension, bradycardia was observed more in SAB group as compared to LSPB group.

In our study results, we observed that LSPB is a safe, effective, standard method of anaesthesia as compared to spinal anaesthesia in high-risk patients such as hypertension, diabetes, ischemic

heart disease, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, chronic renal insufficiency etc. undergoing hip surgeries.

CONCLUSION:

Combined lumbar and sacral plexus block is an effective and safe alternative to SAB as an anaesthetic method for hip surgeries. LSPB offers a more stable perioperative hemodynamics, provides longer duration of postoperative analgesia with less side effects. However, SAB has shorter time for performing the block with earlier sensory and motor block onset. Combined lumbar and sacral plexus block is a favourable alternative to neuraxial and general anaesthesia for elective hip surgeries in high-risk patients.

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